

QUIZ**LAST NAME: NAMUDDU****FIRST NAME: JESSICA****PROGRAM CODE: MDIA****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: SIX (6)****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did did *not*-use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- When carrying out research, one is supposed to plan their first draft and the following is true except.**
 - File away leftovers.
 - Create a plan that meets your readers' needs.
 - Build your argument around answers to readers' questions.¹**
 - Avoid unhelpful plans.
- In the Turabian's "Manual" the structure of an essay should have... Please choose the right choice below:**
 - Introduction, Body, Conclusion.²**
 - Relevant Examples, Body, Conclusion.

¹ Turaban, Kate L. 2013. A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers. Pg. 63 Chicago: The University of Chicago Press Ltd.

² Euclid University. 2015. ACA-401 Coursepack. Pg. 4

- Introduction, Body, Relevant Examples.
- Introduction, Summary, Conclusion.

3. **Quotations refer to...**

- Words that are of the same meaning.
- The exact words of an author.**³
- Ideas and information that an author has produced on a topic.
- Basic rules that one can use in an essay.

4. **A research argument should be based on:**

- Reasons and evidence that support your claim.**⁴
- An amiable conversation in which you and your readers reason together to solve a problem.
- A face-to-face conversation.
- Intuitions, spiritual insights and feelings.

5. **Define the term portfolio as used in research writing.**

- The first sentence of one's writing.
- Any form of collection of writing that has not been taken careful look at.

³ Ibid., 19

⁴ Turabian, Kate L. 2013. A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers. Pg. 37 Chicago: The University of Chicago Press Ltd.

- A carefully chosen collection of work telling the story of one person's journey as a writer.⁵**
- Decisions made quickly by the writer.
6. **Punctuation marks in English writing are always closed up to the preceding word except for:**
- Stops and Dashes.
- Ellipsis and commas.
- All the above.
- Dashes and Ellipsis.⁶**
7. **Abbreviations in the broad sense can be classed into two main categories. Choose the right categories from the given below:**
- Acronyms and Initialisms, Contractions and Truncations.⁷**
- Acronyms and Contractions, Initialisms and Truncations.
- Truncations and Acronyms, Contractions and Initialisms.
- None of the above.
8. **In research writing, there are common errors which researchers/writers usually do, and these include the following.**
- Use of the wrong verb tense.

⁵ Sebranek, Patrick. Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing Thinking and Learning. Pg. 42 (Massachusetts: Great Source Education Group, 1999).

⁶ European Union, 2011. English Style Guide: European Commission Directorate-General for Translation. Pg. 20 Europe: European Commission.

⁷ Ibid., 32

- Using Direct quotes.
- Not proofreading one's work.
- All the above.**⁸

9. **What are the situations under which citation should be provided?**

- When you quote exact words from a source.
- When you paraphrase ideas that are associated with a specific source, even if you don't quote exact words from it.
- When you use any idea, data, or method attributable to any source you consulted.
- All the above.**⁹

10. **In research writing, different notes are used when citing one's work. Which among the following is commonly used?**

- Parenthetical Notes.**¹⁰
- Footnotes.
- Endnotes.
- All the above.

⁸ Euclid University. 2015. ACA-401 Coursepack for Period 4. Pg. 5

⁹ Turabian, Kate L. 2013. A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers. Pg. 86 Chicago: The University of Chicago Press Ltd.

¹⁰ Ibid., 98

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